

ICT Enabled Teaching-Learning Process on Learning Outcomes

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Abstract

Many of the things we do on a daily basis have changed due to advancements in information and communication technology (ICT) in recent years. Thanks to advancements in communication and information technologies, classroom instruction has undergone a radical shift. One goal of incorporating ICTs into education is to raise the bar for education generally by making lessons more engaging and effective for students. In light of the many cultural, social, and economic impacts of computers and the Internet, it is clear that educational institutions must now begin to adopt and employ ICT. When we think about how important ICT is becoming in society, this becomes even more apparent. The internet and other forms of information and communication technology (ICT) open us a world of new possibilities for invention and creativity, and they also allow us to reach today's students in a new way when it comes to the subjects we teach them. Thanks to technological advancements, which save students time and provide them access to new materials, they may now explore topics at a depth that were before impossible. With the advent of modern technology, classrooms have become global village hubs where students and educators may engage in meaningful global conversations centered on common learning goals. The evolution of user-friendly, powerful, and diversely transferable communication and computing systems has made this a reality. A new learning culture could emerge from changes to the structure and approach of the classroom. Information and communication technology (ICT) has created a world where easy and adaptable communication is the standard. Students benefit from ICT in many ways, including the ease with which they may share and access learning resources, the promotion of learner-centered and collaborative learning principles, and the enhancement of their critical, creative, and problem-solving skills. Without a doubt, the world is heading in the direction of education that is dependent on ICT.

Keywords: ICT, Education, Teaching-Learning, Technology, Computer.

Introduction

Someone once said, "Change is the need of development." This is a statement that anybody can agree with. Every single member in our society gradually and steadily became aware of the signs of development that were being shown to them. Every day, throughout this new era, people were forced to contend with challenges that they had never faced before. When folks make an attempt to overcome all of those issues utilising their wits and the support of digital technology, they are consistently doing so. This is because they are continually doing so. During the early stages of the university, it was strictly prohibited for students to use mobile phones and any other types of technology while they were on instructional grounds. At this point in time, however, nobody is aware that mobile would become such a very crucial instrument for classroom education on a day-to-day basis. This miraculous feat was performed by the use of digital technologies. As a result of the fact that students are not permitted to attend school grounds until the symptoms of the Corona outbreak

have been eradicated from society, the educational department did, in fact, give its approval to the use of mobile devices for the purpose of the purpose of conducting online courses on school campuses.

The educational department has given authorization to conduct online classes with the use of information and communication technology. This is due to the fact that pupils are situated in a range of different locations. In order to effectively pre-plan online courses, it is essential for educators to make advantage of the many resources available on the internet. For example, it has been shown that online courses that have been constructed with careful consideration result in excellent learning outcomes¹. For this reason, it is essential for teachers and educational institutions to ensure that all of the information and communication technology (ICT) online resources are accessible to students. This will allow students to study from the convenience of their own homes. There is a possibility that information and communication technology (ICT) may be defined as the convergence of computer networks, telephone networks, and audio-visual networks. This is accomplished by the use of a single cabling or connecting system.

ICT, which stands for information and communication technology, is the fundamental umbrella term that incorporates all communication devices. These devices include, but are not limited to, televisions, mobile phones, computers, network infrastructure, satellite systems, and so on. A number of online courses were made available in the early phases of the development of remote education. A kind of educational programme that is referred to as a "online course" is one in which the majority or all of the content is delivered only via the use of the internet. According to Allen and Seaman chapter 6, "in the majority of instances, there are no meetings that take place in person." Consequently, students who will be attending school or college in the future will be compelled to take classes via the use of the internet. As a result of the education department's ability to run classes at all levels of education, not only in rural areas but also in urban areas, the department is able to provide a higher level of service to its pupils.

ICT for Evaluating Teaching, Learning, And Effectiveness

The term "information and communication technology" (ICT) is frequently used as an abbreviation to refer to any type of technology that is concerned with the transmission or receiving of data. Information and communication technologies are increasingly becoming associated with one another. Because of this, the spectrum of technologies has expanded to cover not just electronic communication methods such as email, MMS, and other forms of electronic communication, but also computers and other devices that are connected to computers.

"ICT" is an abbreviation that stands for "information and communications technology," which is a generic term that refers to the instruments that are utilised to coordinate the numerous types of electronic communication. Telecommunications, broadcast media, intelligent building management systems, audiovisual processing and transmission systems, and control and monitoring via networks are all examples of operations that fall under this category. However, this list is not exhaustive. The term "convergence technology" (CT) is typically defined as the combination of many technologies into a single entity, or the sharing of transmission channels that are capable of accommodating a wide variety of data and communication forms. This is how a significant number of people use the word. Information and communication technology, also known as ICT, is employed in a very fundamental manner in order to improve upon all of the technologies that render communication more straightforward.

The implementation of technology in educational settings is enhancing and contributing to the overall quality of instruction that is being provided. Students are able to acquire information and skills as a consequence of this, which in turn fosters and cultivates critical thinking, creativity, and the ability to study independently. The implementation of information and communication technology (ICT) in the classroom has the potential to enhance students' comprehension of the material being taught. Individuals, companies, and educational institutions will all see a gain in power as a result of the exploitation of information and communication technology.

Importance of ICT in Education:

All individuals who make use of information and communication technology in the modern society want to achieve the same objective, which is the ideal of leading a life that is connected to other people. Internet and communications technology will someday become a lifestyle choice for a sizeable section of the population. Furthermore, this choice of lifestyle is producing a change in the method in which we interact with one another and get information, as well as it is generating an increase in the pace at which we consume.

Information and communication technology (ICT) has the ability to penetrate and affect our lives in a significant way; in fact, we already live in a society that is controlled by technology and is driven by technology.

by consumers. This is because ICT has the ability to invade and revolutionise many aspects of our lives. It is without a doubt that it is a vital component of our lives, and it will continue to be a part of our lives for the foreseeable future. This is true regardless of how we choose to interpret its presence.

ICT Integrated Teaching -Learning Process Uses:

As an additional benefit, it encourages students and teachers to take responsibility for their own education (even when they are attending classes remotely), it increases morale in the classroom, and it gives tools for managing and retrieving data. In the classroom, information and communication technology (ICT) gives students and teachers the opportunity to acquire the competence of being able to operate, store, alter, and retrieve information, which is an essential talent. The use of online classrooms as a way of offering instructional and student-centered learning opportunities is fast gaining favour in the field of higher education. Both expressing the function that information and communication technology plays in the educational arena and offering courses that integrate and blend the demands of both students and teachers are two ways that a person's potential may be achieved. Both of these methods are examples of ways that a person's potential can be realised. Increasing one's level of expertise in certain fields may be accomplished by the use of more specific methods and approaches. demonstrates how essential it is to fulfil educational responsibilities through the utilisation of information and communication technology.

Infrastructural development:

There is a correlation between this incidence and the proliferation of technology, which is in direct opposition to the educational system. As a result of the fact that it is no longer necessary to be physically present in a classroom in order to acquire information, online education has developed into a significant component of the modern educational system. Professionals in the field of education who are willing to educate students who are enrolled in online classes need to have access to appropriate hardware, software, and networks in order to establish online classrooms that provide students an immersive learning experience. For the purpose of providing pupils with a really immersive educational experience, this is very necessary. There are a variety of natural and artificial factors that contribute to the ongoing evolution of the educational system. Some examples of these factors include the passage of time and scientific advancements.

It includes the most recent technical advancements in order to meet the requirements of the general population. Products derived from information and communication technology (ICT) produced in different parts of the world are being utilised in order to make the learning process more efficient. Among the various products that fall under this category, some examples include audio conferencing, teleconferencing, television lectures, radio broadcasts, interactive radio counselling, audiocassettes, CD ROMs, and interactive voice response systems. These are just a few examples. The use of technology into educational settings gives rise to a novel approach to the training of students.

Objectives of the Study-

1. To The Study of Ict Enabled Teaching- Learning
2. To The Study of Importance of Ict in Education

Teachers' Perspectives on Using ICT for Teaching and Learning:

The two most essential components that will influence the decision that teachers make from the enlarged variables that are present around them about how and when they will use a new piece of technology are as follows: These are the two most crucial things that will affect their choice:

In the context of education, the phrase "external variables" refers to the challenges that teachers have while trying to integrate a new technology into their teaching and learning process. These issues are the result of variables that are not within their sphere of influence. There are a number of challenges that are being encountered, including poor accessibility and network connection, schools that do not have enough information and communication technology facilities, a lack of proper training, restricted time, and a lack of teachers' competency.

The term "perceived usefulness" refers to the degree to which the people who are going to utilize a certain technology believe that it will make them more productive and efficient in their performance of their jobs. Teachers utilize a variety of factors to decide whether or not information and communication technology (ICT) technologies are beneficial. Some of these criteria include a quicker completion of work, improved job performance, increased productivity, increased efficacy, and easier use.

The phrase "perceived ease of use" (PEOU) is used to express how customers feel about a system and how much effort they believe it would require to utilise it. As a result of the Impact project and other research, educators have the perception that information and communication technology (ICT) calls for a wide range of skills and competencies. The exact same thing was true for educators. The following are some of the numerous features that it possesses: simplicity in usage, ease of handling, ease of memorising, and ease of learning and comprehension. Among the most important essential factors are the attitudes of teachers towards the use of the tool, the behavioural intentions of staff members, social influence mechanisms (such as job relevance, output quality, result demonstrability, and perceived ease of use), subjective norm, voluntariness, and image, as well as a great number of other factors.

Benefits of Using ICT in Education:

There is a wide variety of electronic distribution systems that fall under the umbrella of ICT, which is an abbreviation that stands for information and communication technology. One of these methods is the use of electronic devices, which includes radios, televisions, projectors, computers, and the Internet, among other applications. The field of education in the current day is one area in which it is utilised widely. Because information and communication technologies are becoming increasingly popular, there is a possibility that more educational possibilities may become available to people. The advancements that have been made in information and communication technology have made it possible for learning to take place at any time and wherever. In the field of education, the utilisation of information and communication technology (ICT) has a multitude of beneficial benefits. For instance, it can make it simpler and quicker for students to locate the information they require online, it can create an environment that encourages students to engage in independent study, it can encourage students to work together even when they are physically separated, it can increase the number of opportunities for students to practise higher-order thinking skills, it can improve the quality of instruction, and it can make course materials more accessible. It is for a variety of reasons that each and every one of these benefits is available. The advancements that have been made in information and communication technology have made it possible for learning and education to make use of digital materials in addition to the more conventional printed ones. Video clips, audio sounds, graphic presentations, and other comparable content are easily accessible on the Internet, making it possible for anybody to acquire new knowledge via their own personal inquiry.

Enhancing learning, motivating and engaging students, promoting collaboration, stimulating inquiry and discovery, and developing a new culture of learning that is focused on the learner are the key goals that are being pursued via the incorporation of information and communication technology (ICT) into pedagogy. Improving the ways in which information and communication technology (ICT) ideas and applications are included into the curriculum of schools is of the utmost importance. This is

due to the fact that information and communication technology provides a greater opportunity for both teachers and students to personalise learning and teaching to the particular needs of each individual.

Instructional strategies for the incorporation of information and communication technologies across the classroom

Within the framework of society, the profession of teaching is seen as one that exudes respect. Educators are able to maintain their knowledge and skills by using information and communication technology (ICT), which allows them to make greater use of the most recent digital tools and resources. It is possible for student teachers to grow into effective educators if they make use of information and communication technology (ICT) and acquire the knowledge required to apply it. The information and communications technology (ICT) business is, without a doubt, one of the most important contributors to the rapid changes that are taking place in our society. As a consequence of this, there is a possibility that the character of education, as well as the roles that students and instructors play in the training and education process, may be transformed. In order to make effective use of information and communication technology in the classroom, one of the tactics that instructors use is to ensure that sufficient infrastructure and technical help are available.

Technology for information and communication should be used in every class.

Through the utilisation of application software, the utilisation of multimedia, Internet e-mail, communities, and the understanding of framework software; Through the implementation of the newly established curriculum for the assessment of pre-service teachers. Over the course of the last several years, teachers in India have started using technology into their classrooms. The use of electronic devices such as laptops, LCD projectors, desktop computers, EDUCOM, smart classrooms, and memory sticks is becoming more frequent in educational institutions for the purpose of teaching. Because of this, the use of information and communication technology (ICT) in the area of teacher education in the 21st century is of the highest relevance. This is due to the fact that teachers have the power to construct a successful future not only for their pupils but also for society by themselves.

When it comes to evaluating or assessing anything specific:

In the field of assessment, the utilisation of information and communications technology (ICT) is becoming more common. This process involves the utilisation of digital devices that provide assistance in the process of developing assessment assignments for students. It is helpful in carrying out responsibilities that are associated with assessment. Not only may students get grades or comments via the use of information and communication technology (ICT), but they can also receive feedback through construction or delivery. It is essential for educational institutions to encourage themselves to strengthen their commitment to developing a more effective evaluation process that may be of use to educators, students, and other stakeholders. The best way for them to do this is to motivate themselves to do so. Most of the time, technology becomes a powerful tool in carrying out operations that are incredibly challenging for a regular human being to evaluate in a short period of time. This is because technology is able to do these activities rapidly. There are a wide variety of activities that cannot be assessed by a computer. These tasks may be broken down into several distinct categories. On the other hand, there are certain jobs that are not appropriate for the computer to analyse whatsoever. One example of a number of different approaches is as follows:

CONCLUSION

"ICT for education" is actually the practice of creating new forms of digital media with the express purpose of enhancing educational opportunities for students. What we mean when we talk about "ICTs in education" is actually just bringing some basic features of technology into the classroom. Finding out how ICT (information and communication technology) would affect schooling in the next years was the driving force for this research. More specifically, ICTs have had a small but noticeable effect on educational practices thus far. However, this is expected to change in the near future, and

ICTs will emerge as a formidable force for transformation in many different areas of education. A number of factors, including the quality and accessibility of education, learning motivation, the learning environment, and the relationship between ICT usage and academic performance, will be profoundly affected by the ongoing development and use of ICTs in education. This finding is derived from the current procedures and actions. Incorporating and making good use of ICTs in educational contexts improves pedagogy, student achievement, and scholarly inquiry. Technology in the classroom has the ability to change how lessons are taught and open them up to more people. It will also make things more adaptable, which means that more students will be able to use the same curriculum. On top of that, it will increase adaptability, allowing students to attend classes despite physical and temporal limitations. It has the potential to influence both the way students are taught and the way they actually learn. Furthermore, it would provide a stimulating environment and motivation for instruction, which seems to significantly impact educational learning by opening up new possibilities for educators and their pupils. Students' performance and achievements might be impacted by these choices. Similarly, classroom instruction and student achievement can both benefit from the widespread dissemination of educational best practices and supplementary resources made possible by advances in information and communication technologies. Overall, the research suggests that when it comes to educational settings, the integration of information and communication technology is a success.

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